

1 A quantitative weight-of-evidence approach for confidence assessment in adverse-outcome pathway

2 networks: Overcoming the barriers

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17 **Abbreviations**

AI	Artificial intelligence
AO	Adverse outcome
AOPs	Adverse outcome pathways
BH	Bradford-Hill
GRADE	Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation
KERs	Key event relationships
MIE	Molecular initiating event
NAMs	New approach methodologies
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
WoE	Weight-of-evidence

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31 **Abstract**

32 Since the concept of next-generation risk assessment was introduced nearly 2 decades ago, international
33 institutions have initiated numerous efforts to enable pathway-based assessment employing new-
34 approach methodologies (NAMs). Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) and their networks serve as
35 pragmatic tools, offering guidance to support both the development of NAMs and regulatory decision-
36 making. Despite their potential, AOPs are still not incorporated into regulatory practices, largely
37 because of concerns about the reliability of information provided. These concerns arise from the
38 common use of expert-driven weight-of-evidence (WoE) confidence evaluations which introduce
39 subjectivity and generate non-reproducible statements on AOP credibility. To address these concerns, a
40 generalizable framework was established covering a semi-automated systematic review for collecting
41 available mechanistic knowledge which is subsequently utilized, to develop an AOP network and
42 evaluate its confidence. The confidence assessment is carried out using an integrative WoE scoring
43 system, aligned with the tailored Bradford-Hill criteria, to quantitatively evaluate the credibility within
44 the AOP. This scoring system is pioneering in quantifying the strength of scientific evidence supporting
45 causality in key event relationships within AOP networks, eliminating the need for expert judgement.
46 This framework forms the foundation for further advancements which can result in a generic,
47 reproducible and versatile tool for simultaneous AOP network development and credibility assessment
48 using synergistic methodologies, ensuring reliable guidance in both regulatory and scientific contexts.
49 The commentary discusses the strengths of the framework and essential future actions including the
50 complete automation of systematic reviews and the continued refinement of the weighting, scoring and
51 rating system covered by the WoE strategy.

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53 **Key words:** adverse outcome pathways, weight-of-evidence, Bradford-Hill criteria, systematic
54 reviews

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56 **1. Regulatory acceptance of AOPs**

57 The U.S. National Research Council report “Toxicity Testing in the 21st Century” in 2007, marked the
58 beginning of a major transition toward next-generation risk assessment, emphasizing pathway-based
59 assessment using new-approach methodologies (Krewski et al., 2010, 2020). To date, this shift remains
60 a priority, with both the U.S. Food and Drug Administration and the European Commission
61 underscoring its ongoing urgency (FDA, 2025; Walder et al., 2025). The concept of pathway-based
62 approaches was further expanded with the introduction of adverse outcome pathways (AOPs). AOPs
63 are frameworks structuring the existing mechanistic information underpinning biological linkages in a
64 sequential manner. More specifically, the interaction between a chemical and a biological target, usually
65 at the molecular level, is identified as the molecular initiating event (MIE). This event is connected to
66 the adverse outcome (AO) observed at the population level through a series of key events (KEs)
67 occurring at the cellular and tissue levels (Ankley et al., 2010; Villeneuve et al., 2014). Initially, AOPs
68 were developed as linear constructs, limiting their ability to reflect biological complexity. This
69 limitation was overcome by AOP networks, which link AOPs that share one or more KEs to better
70 capture the interactions within living organisms. To date, over 500 AOPs have been developed and are
71 stored in an AOP knowledge base, accessible via the AOPWiki (<https://aopwiki.org/>). AOPs and their
72 networks are versatile tools, finding applications in both scientific and regulatory contexts, with a strong
73 interest as guidance to support the development of NAMs for chemical risk assessment (Arnesdotter et
74 al. 2022; Vinken 2024; Leist et al. 2017). However, their use in regulatory settings remains limited due
75 to insufficient confidence in the quality of information provided by AOPs. To enable their regulatory
76 use, it is crucial to regularly update AOPs with newly generated mechanistic data and evaluate their
77 credibility. This reflects the strength and extent of evidence supporting the causality in relationships
78 between KEs (KERs) in an AOP and is typically evaluated through a weight-of-evidence (WoE)
79 confidence assessment. One key reason for this distrust is that AOPs have traditionally relied on
80 mechanistic data selected by domain experts, along with expert-driven qualitative WoE approaches.
81 These methodologies lack transparency, reproducibility and objectivity, which are crucial elements for
82 their standardization and harmonisation (Bajard et al., 2023; Coady et al., 2019). To improve the

83 acceptance of AOPs and their networks in regulatory settings, generic WoE approaches are needed
84 during their development and confidence evaluation.

85 **2. Challenges of WoE methodologies**

86 To assess the strength of the causal relationships in an AOP, WoE confidence approaches are typically
87 based on the tailored Bradford-Hill (BH) criteria described by guidelines of the Organization for
88 Economic Co-operation and Development (Meek et al., 2014; OECD, 2018; Schunemann et al., 2011).
89 These confidence approaches combine multiple lines of evidence to assess the credibility in the AOP.
90 The integration of the lines of evidence should be carried out in a standardized manner to ensure
91 consistency and comparability across different operators (Linkov et al., 2015). Qualitative methods such
92 as “Guided Expert Judgement” are often utilized entailing expert reviewing of the 3 tailored BH criteria
93 (*i.e.*, biological plausibility, essentiality and empirical evidence), providing a statement on the
94 credibility of the evidence supporting the AOP (Collier et al., 2016; Linkov et al., 2015). Over the past
95 decade, efforts have been directed toward developing more quantitative approaches that enable the
96 numerical evaluation of collected evidence. These include applying weighting methods to the tailored
97 BH criteria and scoring individual lines of evidence, which can then be integrated by using techniques
98 such as “Multi Criteria Decision Analysis”. Thereby, improving the transparency and reproducibility of
99 AOP development and confidence assessment (Becker et al., 2015, 2017; Collier et al., 2016; Linkov
100 et al., 2015). However, these proposed quantitative methods still rely on professional judgement to
101 assign weights and scores to the tailored BH criteria and evidence, respectively, before applying
102 mathematical models, making them susceptible to bias (Becker et al., 2017; Collier et al., 2016). The
103 Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) workshop held in
104 2019 highlighted that, in addition to this challenge, AOP development and evaluation could benefit from
105 a synergistic approach that incorporates systematic review methods applying machine learning and
106 artificial intelligence (AI) techniques. This integrated approach would assure more transparency,
107 objectivity and comprehensiveness of the evidence underpinning an AOP (de Vries et al., 2021;
108 Hoffmann et al., 2022).

109 To overcome these challenges and support the regulatory use of AOPs and their networks, a framework
110 combining methodologies for their development and evaluation is proposed (Van Ertvelde et al., 2023;
111 Verhoeven et al., 2024). This framework incorporates a semi-automated systematic review methodology
112 for extracting mechanistic data to support the development and evaluation of AOP networks. It also
113 integrates a quantitative WoE confidence approach with a scoring system designed to determine the
114 level of credibility in KERs within an AOP network without expert judgement. This commentary
115 outlines the key strengths and advancements achieved through this framework and the challenges that
116 still need to be overcome. The technical details concerning the execution of AOP network development
117 and evaluation using this framework are provided in the corresponding papers (Van Ertvelde et al.,
118 2023; Verhoeven et al., 2024).

119 **3. Strengths of the proposed framework for AOP network development and confidence** 120 **assessment**

121 A framework was outlined covering a semi-automated systematic review to capture newly available
122 mechanistic data on, in this case, chemical-induced steatosis and cholestasis (Van Ertvelde et al., 2023;
123 Verhoeven et al., 2024). Employing a systematic review approach enables the comprehensive collection
124 of available knowledge, including contradictory evidence, thereby enhancing objectivity instead of
125 relying on selective papers to support traditional expert-driven confidence assessment. The retrieved
126 mechanistic data from the systematic review was subsequently used to both update existing AOP
127 networks and to provide evidence for evaluating the credibility in the networks through a quantitative
128 WoE confidence approach entailing an integrative scoring system.

129 3.1. Semi-automated systematic review

130 For the collection of mechanistic data, PubMed was selected as a database to query data published after
131 the initial AOP network. To define appropriate MeSH terms, the AOPWiki database was used to include
132 all biological events associated with the AO. Thereafter, the retrieved papers were uploaded on SysRev
133 to enable automated title/abstract screening. SysRev is a free AI-based platform for data curation and
134 systematic evidence reviews, which has shown effectiveness in automatically including abstracts based
135 on predictions derived from prior manual screening (Bozada et al., 2021). For the initial title/abstract

136 screening, Boolean labels were created as eligibility criteria to include relevant research papers covering
137 mechanistic information (*i.e.*, data related to KEs) on the AO of interest. The machine learning
138 algorithm within SysRev was first trained *via* manual label assignment. When the model's performance,
139 measured through inclusion probability, reached an adequate threshold, set at 60% in this case, the
140 remaining papers were screened automatically. The use of AI-based platforms enhances the efficiency
141 of systematic reviews by accelerating title/abstract screening while reducing selection bias associated
142 with manual inclusion. Full-text review for curating mechanistic data was conducted manually in
143 SysRev, as automatic data extraction was not available at the time of the studies. However, SysRev
144 supports data labelling and extraction in line with the FAIR (*i.e.*, Findability, Accessibility,
145 Interoperability and Reuse) principles. To further standardize data extraction across reviewers, a
146 labelling system was developed that applies group labels to facilitate structured data extraction. This
147 approach ensures transparency and reproducibility in the process. The labelling system applied
148 categorical labels for existing KEs and string labels for novel KEs, assisting AOP development through
149 systematic KE identification. The labelling system also included categorical labels, each linked to
150 specific questions aligned with the tailored BH criteria, supplying evidence for the subsequent WoE
151 confidence assessment (OECD, 2018). Prior to data extraction, a full-text screening was performed to
152 exclude false positives resulting from the automated title/abstract screening and for the suitability for
153 data extraction. After the data extraction, SysRev allows to export the group labels as datasets, with the
154 data organized in a tabular form. More specifically, each row in the table represents a line of evidence
155 corresponding to a KER including the upstream and downstream KE along with their supporting
156 evidence for causality.

157 3.2. Scoring-based integration for quantitative WoE assessment

158 The proposed integrative scoring system is pivotal in enabling the quantification of the level of scientific
159 evidence supporting the causality in KER within AOP networks without manual assignment of scores
160 in an transparent and reproducible manner. For each tailored BH criterion, a corresponding scoring
161 system was designed. Each system included a customized equation aligned with the associated
162 questions of the tailored BH criterion, allowing a numerical value to be assigned for each criterion per

163 line of evidence independently of expert judgement. The scores for each criterion were normalized and
164 integrated by summation into a total causality score for each unique KER in the AOP network. These
165 scores help identify KERs supported by the strongest evidence, as well as indicating their degree of
166 readiness for practical application in regulatory contexts. High numerical values reflect an abundance
167 of consistent mechanistic evidence supporting causality within KERs, establishing them as key focus
168 areas for regulatory decision-making and for the development of NAMs intended for chemical safety
169 assessment. In contrast, lower values indicate limited mechanistic insight or inconsistent data, thereby
170 highlighting critical gaps in the current understanding of the AO and thus identify priorities for further
171 fundamental research.

172 3.2.1. Biological plausibility

173 The biological plausibility criterion evaluates whether the causal link in the proposed KER is
174 biologically consistent and scientifically valid (OECD, 2018). Therefore, the labelling system used
175 categorical labels to extract data on the biological application domain and correlation between the KEs
176 among the papers. The former indicates the extent to which an unique KER is applicable across
177 chemicals, species, test systems, and types of evidence. The scoring system counted the distinct
178 categories represented. A higher score obtained for the biological application domain thus reflects
179 broader applicability across these contexts. The correlation represents the occurrence of a positive,
180 negative or non-existing/non-established relationship between KEs. The proportion of the lines of
181 evidence for an unique KER identifying a positive or negative correlation were calculated across the
182 dataset in the equation. A score of 1 or -1 denotes consistent reporting of a positive or negative
183 correlation, respectively, for that unique KER. Values between 0 and 1, 0 and -1 reflect inconsistencies
184 in the supporting evidence, while a value of 0 indicates either that the correlation was not measured or
185 that opposing assignments cancelled each other, so no correlation can be inferred. This proportion was
186 subsequently multiplied by the frequency of the unique KER in the dataset, thereby allowing the body
187 of evidence to contribute to the overall score. To obtain a single score for biological plausibility, the
188 scores for correlation and biological application domain were summarized in the equation.

189 3.2.2. Empirical evidence

190 The empirical evidence criterion assess the causal link in a KER by evaluating the concordance in the
191 data regarding dose-response, temporality and incidence. In this regard, the labelling system included
192 Boolean labels to identify the existence of dose- and time-concordance across the included papers. The
193 equation within the scoring system determined the proportions for the existence and non-existence of
194 these concordances across the lines of evidence for an unique KE in the dataset. In case the obtained
195 scores for dose- and/or time-concordance exceeded 0, the existence of concordance was assumed.
196 Reversely, a negative or 0 value indicated a non-existing or non-established concordance for time and
197 or dose. The proportions were as well multiplied by the frequency of the unique KER. The overall score
198 for empirical evidence for a unique KER was calculated by leveraging its scores for dose- and time-
199 concordance, with higher scores reflecting stronger evidence which substantiates the connection.

200 3.2.3. Essentiality

201 The essentiality criterion evaluates whether the upstream KE is critical for progression within a KER,
202 based on evidence that its prevention, inhibition, or modification alters the downstream KE. Scoring
203 this criterion requires considering both the observed correlation between the KEs and the experimental
204 setup in which it was demonstrated. Therefore, the labelling system incorporated categorical and string
205 labels to capture this information from the included papers. Following the OECD guidelines, the scoring
206 system assigned higher scores to correlations supported by direct evidence (*e.g.*, knockout models) than
207 to those based on indirect evidence. Within the equation, the proportions for positive and negative
208 correlations found by direct and indirect evidence were calculated across the lines of evidence for an
209 unique KER. Thereafter, the score was multiplied with the number of unique research articles that
210 assessed the KER.

211 4. Future considerations

212 This framework addressed a critical need highlighted during the GRADE meeting in 2019, however, its
213 limitations emphasize the need for future advancements to further enhance its objectivity, transparency,
214 and reproducibility.

215 4.1. Fully automated systematic review

216 The framework comprises a semi-automated systematic review that integrates machine learning
217 techniques to automatically include papers through title/abstract screening within SysRev. A noted
218 limitation lies in the reliance on a single database (*i.e.*, PubMed) during the literature search. While
219 PubMed is a peer-reviewed database, it does not encompass all available resources containing valuable
220 mechanistic data. Moreover, limiting the query to a certain date further reduced the available body of
221 evidence. Automatic inclusion using machine learning tools was applied at the title/abstract screening
222 stage. Although using predefined standardized labels, data extraction was still performed manually, and
223 potentially introducing inter-researcher bias and variability in label assignment. Data extraction
224 automation would therefore reduce the most manual-intensive step during systematic reviews. To date,
225 there is a lack of applications utilizing text mining and machine learning techniques for data extraction,
226 such as natural language processing (Scotti et al., 2025; Yang et al., 2023). SysRev, however, shows
227 potential in facilitating the extraction of specific terms through its integration of various natural
228 language processing tools (Bozada et al., 2021). This potential should be further explored by initially
229 advancing towards the integration of machine learning with rule based-methods and human supervision
230 ensuring accuracy and reliability in data extraction (Ram et al., 2022; Scotti et al., 2025).

231 4.2. Quality evaluation of extracted data

232 Assessing the quality of mechanistic data extracted from various types of studies is essential for
233 evaluating the validity of the corresponding study's estimated effect, yet this aspect is currently lacking
234 in the proposed framework. In toxicology, a critical determinant of study quality is the risk of bias,
235 which often arises from shortcomings in the study design, execution, analysis, or reporting (Hartung et
236 al., 2025; Hoffmann et al., 2022). The Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool is most widely used for bias
237 assessment, traditionally for clinical research and has later been adapted for toxicology such as the
238 OHAT Risk of Bias Tool (OHAT, 2019). Specialized tools including the ToxRTool and SciRAP have
239 been developed and adapted to address the methodological complexities inherent in toxicology studies.
240 Both tools are applied for data originating from *in vitro* and *in vivo* toxicological studies, ToxRTool
241 provides detailed criteria for assessing data reliability and quality, while SciRAP offers criteria for
242 evaluating the relevance and application domain (Segal et al., 2015; Waspe et al., 2021). Although these

243 are validated tools, they are time-intensive and rely heavily on expert judgement, which introduces a
244 degree of subjectivity and increases their susceptibility to evaluation bias (Hartung et al., 2025).
245 Because these tools share common features, they can be made machine-readable to enable automated
246 bias assessment. Indeed, a recent publication outlines potential AI-based approaches for identifying
247 various types of bias within toxicology studies, accompanied by promising case studies (Hartung et al.,
248 2025). Implementing an AI-based bias assessment as a quality parameter, alongside a numerical scoring
249 system to evaluate the overall validity of each study during the systematic review process, will indicate
250 the reliability of extracted mechanistic data for subsequent use in the development and evaluation of
251 AOP networks.

252 4.3. Quantification of WoE frameworks

253 4.3.1. A weighing system for the tailored BH criteria

254 Within the current WoE framework, all tailored BH criteria are assumed to have an equal importance
255 and were therefore not assigned with weights. However, according to the OECD guidelines, biological
256 plausibility is considered the most determinative criterion in assessing the credibility of the AOP
257 network followed by essentiality and empirical evidence (OECD, 2018). Numerical weights should
258 therefore be assigned to each criterion to reflect their hierarchical ranking and subsequently their
259 relative contribution to the total score obtained in the scoring system. Becker et al. described such a
260 numerical system, emphasizing how varying weighting factors for the tailored BH criteria influence the
261 credibility assessment through sensitivity analyses (Becker et al., 2017). The proposed WoE framework
262 can adopt a similar approach by performing sensitivity analyses to evaluate how the chosen weighting
263 factors for the tailored BH criteria affect the overall confidence score obtained by the integrative scoring
264 system, thereby indicating the most appropriate weights.

265 4.3.2. An integrative scoring system for the evidence

266 The developed scoring system, integrating 3 distinct equations customized for each tailored BH
267 criterion, utilized the body of evidence gathered through a systematic review to generate objective and
268 transparent numerical scores for each unique KER. These equations, however, overly emphasize the

269 incidence of unique KERs across the dataset, which skews the resulting scores and thereby introduce
270 interpretation bias. This can be addressed by replacing the incidence of a unique KER in the equations
271 with a weighting value that reflects both its frequency and overall validity across supporting studies. In
272 this context, the quality parameter discussed above could be utilized as it can reflect the cumulative
273 validity of studies for each unique KER. To obtain an objective, reproducible and transparent quality
274 weighting value for each unique KER, further efforts have to focus on the integration of both frequency
275 and validity.

276 4.3.3. A rating system to categorize the evidence

277 After calculating the total confidence score for each KER within the AOP network, a rating system is
278 applied to categorize the supporting evidence as low, moderate, or high confidence, providing an overall
279 statement of confidence (OECD, 2018). The current WoE framework utilized a tertile-based rating
280 method to categorize the evidence, chosen to reduce subjectivity compared with traditional expert
281 judgement. However, the use of different cut-off values can yield varying confidence levels for the same
282 KER. This underscores the need for more objective and automated categorizing methodologies within
283 WoE assessment. Supervised models covering machine learning classification models such as Support
284 Vector Machines can be utilized to categorize numerical scores into high, moderate and low (Guo et al.,
285 2023). This process initially requires training the model on, preferably, historical data in which KER
286 scores have already been labelled with these classifications. However, such domain-specific data remain
287 scarce to date. One approach to address this challenge is to train the models on similar types of datasets
288 with comparable features and meaning of categories. This can introduce selection and misclassification
289 bias when the training data is not sufficient representative or qualitative (Bayram & Ahmed, 2023;
290 Hartung et al., 2025). An alternative approach may initially integrate machine learning models with
291 expert-derived input to provide structure and domain knowledge, which the model then uses to refine
292 its classification (Wehenkel et al., 2023).

293

294 **5. Conclusion**

295 A proposed WoE framework covering a semi-automated systematic review coupled to an integrative
296 scoring system enables the simultaneous development of AOP networks and their credibility assessment
297 in a more transparent and objective manner. The potential of this framework has been previously
298 demonstrated through 2 case studies on hepatotoxicity indicating its applicability across different AOs.
299 This framework forms the foundation for further advancements, including the complete automation of
300 systematic reviews and the continuous refinement of the weighting, scoring and rating system. These
301 improvements indicate the potential to deliver a generic, reproducible and versatile tool for
302 simultaneous AOP network development and credibility assessment using synergistic methodologies,
303 ensuring more reliable guidance in both regulatory and scientific contexts.

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